

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE ASSESSMENT OF THE NEED FOR PALLIATIVE AND HOSPICE CARE IN UKRAINE

Valentyna NESTERENKO¹ [0000-0002-3773-9525],

Victor OHNIEV² [0000-0003-3423-9303]

¹candidate of medical sciences, associate professor of the department of Public Health and Health Care Management of Kharkiv National Medical University,

vh.nesterenko@kntmu.edu.ua

²doctor of medical sciences, professor, head of the department of Public Health and Health Care Management of Kharkiv National Medical University.

va.ohniev@kntmu.edu.ua

The provision of palliative and hospice care (PHC) is associated with significant financial costs of the state budget, if countries pay the necessary attention to these types of care [1]. Ukraine strives for a model of increasing PHC coverage of those categories of patients recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) as best practices [2]. This is especially important in the context of the growing number of patients in need of PHC both in Ukraine and around the world [3]. Thus, the WHO expects an increase the need for PHC by 2040 in the world by 25–47%.

In our study [4] the need for the main types of PHC for the population of Ukraine in 2018–2020 was determined. The study was carried out according to the methodology proposed by the Ukrainian Center for Public Data [5]. The methodology involves the use of data from national statistics centers (the State Statistics Service of Ukraine [6] and the Public Health Center of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine [7]), national cancer and tuberculosis registries [8; 9] (mainly on the number of deaths and those discharged from hospitals with the corresponding diagnosis), to which empirical coefficients from 0.2 to 0.9 are applied, determined by experts.

As a result of the research, we determined the absolute values and trends regarding the need for the main PHC types for adults and children of Ukraine in 2018–2020. The need in absolute values among adults was 227,143; 212,199 and 190,179, among children – 61,355; 49,002 and 45,357, respectively. The data are presented in the Table.

Table. The need for palliative and hospice care among adults and children of Ukraine in 2018–2020

Year	Category of patients		
	adults	children	total
2018	227,143	61,355	288,498
2019	212,199	49,002	261,201
2020	190,179	45,357	235,536

The greatest need for PHC among adults during this period was noted for malignant neoplasms and cardiovascular diseases, and among children – for congenital malformations, certain perinatal conditions, cerebral palsy, and malignant neoplasms. The overall need for PHC had a steady downward trend both among adults (by 16.27%) and among children (by 26.07%). The largest relative declines among adults during this period were recorded for rheumatoid arthritis, diabetes, and HIV/AIDS, and among children – for congenital malformations, inflammatory diseases of the central nervous system, and cardiovascular diseases.

The calculation method, as well as the very idea of conducting this research, are innovative. However, during the research we identified a number of methodological problems, which we are currently working on solving:

- there are no clear criteria for determining empirical coefficients in calculations of the need for PHC, determined by experts;
- the national tuberculosis register has not updated the data for a long time;
- the database of the national cancer register is inconvenient for finding the necessary information;
- data from the State Statistics Service of Ukraine and the Public Health Center of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine contain different indexes used in the calculations for the same years;

- the data on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease used in the calculations most likely contain a significant part of the cases of deaths from COVID-19, which should be calculated separately.

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